

Symposium
|
**OPEN SCIENCE
IN QUALITATIVE
RESEARCH**

25 SEPTEMBER 2025

UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP
STADSCAMPUS

While open science is already widely embraced in quantitative research, its implementation in qualitative research requires a more tailored approach. Interest in open science in qualitative research is growing rapidly, and experiences are becoming increasingly rich and diverse. This one-day event centers on open science in qualitative research, addressing both the opportunities and the challenges involved in making qualitative research more open, respecting the specific nature of qualitative methodologies. In the morning sessions, we focus on the broader landscape of open science in qualitative research, including policy developments, the funder perspective, and ethical considerations. In the afternoon, we aim to address and overcome common challenges by engaging participants in hands-on open science practices in qualitative research that have shown to be effective.

8h30 to 9h00	REGISTRATION
9h00 to 9h15	WELCOME AND INTRODUCTORY NOTE <i>Prof. Dr. Esther van Zimmerman</i> Chair UA Open Science Committee
9h15 to 10h00	PLENARY SESSION Funding the future FWO's perspective on open science and qualitative research <i>Dr. Olivier Boehme</i>
10h00 to 10h15	COFFEE BREAK
10h15 to 11h15	PLENARY SESSION Ethical considerations of open science in qualitative research EASHW <i>Prof. Dr. Charlotte De Backer</i>
11h30 to 12h30	PLENARY SESSION Navigating the data continuum From closed to open in qualitative research <i>Linde Tuybens</i>
12h30 to 13h30	LUNCH
13h30 to 15h00	PLENARY SESSION Open science in qualitative research Challenges and enablers <i>Dr. Nicki Lisa Cole</i>
15h00 to 16h00	INTERACTIVE WORKSHOPS Workshop I Pre-registration in qualitative research <i>Prof. Dr. Tamarinde Haven</i> Workshop II Auditing quality in qualitative research <i>Bea Mertens</i>
16h00 to 16h15	COFFEE BREAK
16h15 to 17h00	PLENARY SESSION Panel discussion Echoes from the sessions
17h00 to 18h00	NETWORK RECEPTION

THE TEAM BEHIND THE EVENT

This event is organized by Bea Mertens, Linde Tuybens, and Eline Vandewalle.

PLENARY SESSIONS

● **Dr. Olivier Boehme**

Dr. Olivier Boehme is coordinator of the Strategy and Policy Unit and a member of the Executive Committee of the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO). He holds a PhD in History (University of Antwerp, 2007) and is currently involved in shaping the FWO's funding programmes. A key new development in this regard is the broadening of the concept of scientific excellence. In addition, the FWO is integrating open science into its research support policy. Both themes show significant points of convergence and will be discussed during his talk.

● **Prof. Dr. Charlotte De Backer**

Prof. Dr. Charlotte De Backer is chair of the Ethics Committee for the Social Sciences and Humanities. She will lead a session on the ethical considerations of open science in qualitative research. In her contribution, she will address the challenges and opportunities of integrating ethical reflection into open science practices, with a particular focus on the specificities of qualitative research.

● **Linde Tuybens**

Linde Tuybens is a Research Data Management expert at the Research Affairs Office (part of RIVA), where she specifically supports researchers in the social sciences and humanities. With a background in cultural history, she brings a strong connection to these fields to her role as research data steward. She provides training on open data, FAIR principles, and data management planning, with a particular focus on integrating qualitative research practices. She is a supporting member of the university's Open Science Committee and represents the University of Antwerp in the VLIR working group on Open Science & Research Data Management.

● **Dr. Nicki Lisa Cole**

Dr. Nicki Lisa Cole is a senior researcher at the Know Center Research in Graz, Austria and a member of the Open and Reproducible Research Group. She is a sociologist whose work centers on promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in the shift toward Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. She is also one of the founding members of the Open Qualitative Research Community, a network dedicated to advancing openness in qualitative research practices. In her talk, Dr. Cole will explore the challenges qualitative researchers encounter when engaging with open science initiatives, such as data sharing, preregistration, and the development of data management plans. She will address the current imbalance within open science, where the emphasis is often placed on open outputs—such as accessible publications or datasets—while open processes receive far less attention. While the availability of open outputs is undoubtedly valuable, Dr. Cole argues that without parallel efforts to make research processes transparent, the broader goals of reproducibility and replicability remain difficult to achieve. She will provide an overview of terminology or key concepts, challenges, and enablers in opening up qualitative research.

WORKSHOPS

● **Dr. Tamarinde Haven**

Dr. Tamarinde Haven is affiliated as an assistant professor with Tilburg University. She is a research integrity advocate and currently works on strengthening rigor in mixed methods research. She is also one of the founding members of the Open Qualitative Research Community, a network dedicated to advancing openness in qualitative research practices. One of her key contributions is promoting pre-registration in qualitative studies—a practice traditionally associated with quantitative research but

adapted for qualitative methods to improve transparency and trust. Pre-registration in qualitative research involves documenting the research plan before data collection, which helps clarify intentions, prevent selective reporting, and reinforce methodological rigor.

In the workshop *Pre-registration in qualitative research* participants will not only learn how pre-registration applies to their field of study but also receive hands-on practical examples (templates developed by Dr. Tamarinde Haven), which will be helpful to start implementing pre-registration in their research. This workshop also aims to encourage attendees to reflect on both the advantages and challenges of preregistration in qualitative research.

Bea Mertens ●

Bea Mertens is a PhD researcher in Educational Sciences, studying the learning processes of low-educated adults. In her doctoral work, she attaches great importance to research integrity and actively applies open science principles. For the qualitative studies in her project, she explored how open science can be meaningfully implemented and developed a workable format for audit trailing to make quality checks more explicit and the research process more transparent. These ideas will also be discussed in the workshop *Auditing Quality in Qualitative Research*.

CO-ORGANIZER

Eline Vandewalle

Eline Vandewalle is a PhD researcher in the field of bibliometrics, with an interest in publication practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities, multilingualism and societal impact. She works for ECOOM (Expertise Centre for Research & Development Monitoring, where she provides support for the VABB-SHW (the Flemish Bibliographic Database for the Social Sciences and Humanities). She wrote a report on Open Access and Peer Review, and maintains a general interest in open science practices.